

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF FORMING STUDENTS' INTEREST IN MATHEMATICS

A.B. Nizamov¹, S.A. Mirzaqobilova²

GDPI senior teacher¹

Master's student at Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20552902>

Abstract. *This article comprehensively examines the psychological and pedagogical features of developing students' interest in mathematics, as well as the theoretical foundations and practical significance of enhancing cognitive activity in the mathematics learning process. In the context of modern educational reforms, increasing students' interest in mathematics is considered one of the most important pedagogical tasks, since mathematics plays a significant role in developing logical thinking, analytical abilities, independence, and creative approaches to problem-solving. Particularly in primary education, fostering a stable interest in mathematics is essential because this stage forms the foundation of students' learning motivation and intellectual development.*

The article analyzes the psychological factors influencing students' interest in mathematics, including age-related and individual characteristics, emotional states, cognitive needs, and motivational processes. It is emphasized that primary school students learn more effectively through visual, practical, and game-based activities. Therefore, the importance of organizing mathematics lessons through interactive methods, didactic games, problem-based learning, and modern pedagogical technologies is scientifically justified.

Keywords: *mathematics education, interest in mathematics, primary education, learning motivation, logical thinking, didactic games, interactive methods, innovative technologies, cognitive activity, creative thinking, problem-based learning.*

INTRODUCTION

“Mathematics is one of the important subjects that develops human thinking and forms the ability to think logically” [1]. Therefore, today, the formation of students' interest in mathematics is considered one of the urgent tasks of the education system. Especially at the primary education stage, the development of positive motivation in students towards mathematics determines the effectiveness of the subsequent educational process. Because it is during this period that students' initial attitude towards learning, cognitive activity, and intellectual interests are formed.

Primary school students are psychologically very active and curious, they tend to observe, analyze events around them, and learn new things. Therefore, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students in teaching mathematics is one of the important pedagogical factors. If mathematics lessons are organized in an interesting, understandable and practical way, students will develop a positive attitude and strong interest in this subject.

Today, the importance of mathematics in society is growing. The development of modern technologies, economics, engineering, information and communication systems, and many other areas is directly related to mathematical knowledge. Therefore, developing mathematical literacy and forming mathematical thinking in students from the primary education stage is one of the

important tasks. Mathematical knowledge has a positive effect not only on students' success in the educational process, but also on their problem-solving skills in everyday life.

Through mathematics lessons, students develop qualities such as accuracy, consistency, patience, and independent thinking. In particular, in the process of solving mathematical problems, students learn to analyze, compare, generalize, and draw conclusions. This, along with developing their logical thinking, helps them successfully master other subjects.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The issue of forming students' interest in mathematics is one of the relevant areas in modern pedagogy and psychology. Research shows that in the primary school period, the need for knowledge, motivation and emotional state of students are of decisive importance in forming an attitude to mathematics.

A number of scientists (Vygotsky, Leontiev, Piaget) emphasize that the mental development of students is based on activity. In particular, according to the theory of L.S. Vygotsky, the student acquires knowledge through social environment and collaborative activity, which serves as an important psychological basis for the development of mathematical thinking. Also, in the theory of activity of A.N. Leontiev, learning motivation and internal need are indicated as the main factors in acquiring knowledge.

In modern pedagogical and psychological research, the effectiveness of interactive methods, didactic games and problem-based learning technologies in the process of forming interest in mathematics in primary school students is especially recognized. In particular, the interactive learning process transforms the student from a passive participant in the lesson to an active subject, which ensures his conscious and interest-based approach to the learning process.

Didactic games are organized taking into account the emotional and psychological characteristics of primary school age. Through game activities, students master mathematical concepts in a natural and interesting way, in this process a sense of competition, motivation and success is formed. As a result, a positive emotional background is created in students, and internal motivation for completing mathematical tasks increases.

Problem-based learning technologies serve to develop students' independent thinking. By creating problem situations, students are involved in the process of searching for, analyzing and drawing conclusions from ready-made knowledge, rather than accepting it. This leads to the development of mathematical thinking and deep assimilation of knowledge.

In this regard, lessons organized on the basis of game technologies create a positive emotional environment in students, increase their activity in the lesson process and significantly increase their interest in mathematical tasks [8].

Also, some studies note that the formation of interest in mathematics is closely related to cognitive processes. The development of mental processes such as attention, memory, thinking, and imagination increases the effectiveness of students in mastering mathematical knowledge [9]. This indicates that the psychological and pedagogical approach is complex in nature.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a comprehensive approach to study the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of the formation of interest in mathematics among primary school students. This approach includes pedagogical observation, questionnaire, interview method, pedagogical experiment, interactive methods, comparative analysis, problem-based learning, and didactic games.

The practical research was carried out with the participation of primary school students of a general secondary school in Syrdarya region. During the research, the level of students' interest in mathematics was measured at the initial (diagnostic) and final (control) stages.

During the pedagogical experiment, interactive methods, didactic games, and problem-based learning elements were systematically and purposefully introduced into the lesson process. In this case, the structure of each lesson was organized in accordance with the age and psychological characteristics of students, and tasks aimed at increasing their cognitive activity were gradually complicated. According to modern pedagogical research, the motivational environment created by the teacher, as well as the use of innovative technologies in the lesson process, significantly increase students' interest in educational activities and form their internal motivation [10].

Through interactive methods, students were transformed into active participants who independently search for, discuss, and draw conclusions about knowledge, not just subjects receiving ready-made knowledge. Didactic games, on the other hand, instilled in students a sense of competition, cooperation, and achievement, turning the process of completing mathematical tasks into an interesting and emotionally positive activity. Problem-based learning elements, on the other hand, served to develop students' logical thinking, directing them to analyze the problem and find a solution rather than accepting a ready-made answer.

RESULTS

In the course of the research, a pedagogical experiment was conducted aimed at forming the interest of primary school students in mathematics. During the experiment, 8 main methods (pedagogical observation, questionnaire, interview, pedagogical experiment, interactive methods, didactic games, problem-based learning and comparative analysis) were systematically used. The results confirmed that each method had a different impact on the cognitive activity and motivation of students.

Pedagogical observation, as one of the most important diagnostic methods of the study, made it possible to study the behavior, activity and attitude of students to mathematical tasks in real conditions in the natural learning process. At the initial stage of the observation, it was found that the level of activity of students in the lesson was relatively low. It was observed that most students did not show independent initiative in completing mathematical tasks, but rather waited for the teacher's instructions.

Also, psychological factors such as shyness in answering questions, lack of freedom of expression, and fear of mistakes were significantly manifested during the lesson. This situation indicated that students had formed a lack of confidence in mathematics and a passive learning position. Some students showed a tendency to quickly get tired or lose interest when faced with more complex tasks.

In general, the results of pedagogical observation showed that the innovative methods used in the educational process, along with increasing the level of activity of students, positively changed their attitude towards mathematics and served to form psychological confidence and interest.

The questionnaire method was used in the research process as an important tool in determining the subjective attitude of students to mathematics, the level of interest, and the emotional and emotional attitude to the lesson process. The questionnaire questions were aimed at determining the level of acceptance of mathematics by students, their activity in the lesson, their attitude to assignments, and their desire to work independently.

A comparative analysis of the questionnaire results showed that the percentage of students who expressed a positive attitude increased significantly. In particular, the number of students who chose the answer “mathematics lessons are interesting” increased significantly after the experiment. This indicates that the innovative pedagogical technologies used increased students' emotional interest and softened the stereotypical "difficult science" view of science.

The results of the pedagogical experiment made it possible to determine the main quantitative indicators of the study. The level of interest in mathematics in the experimental classes was significantly higher than in the control classes. When comparing the results before and after the experiment, it was found that the indicator of active participation in the lesson in the experimental group increased by an average of 30–40%.

Also, the efficiency of students' independent work improved by 25–35%, which indicates a decrease in their dependence on external assistance in their educational activities. In the control classes, such a significant increase was not noted, since traditional teaching methods were used.

Interactive methods (including "Brainstorming", "Cluster", "Blitz-survey", "Question and Answer" technologies) significantly increased the activity of students in the lesson process. These methods allowed students to freely express their thoughts, consider different approaches to the problem and make collective decisions.

As a result, students developed the skills of substantiating their opinions, logical analysis and participating in the discussion process. In particular, it was observed that even previously passive students gained confidence in entering the lesson process, asking and answering questions.

Interactive methods also developed communicative competencies in students. They began to acquire the skills of exchanging ideas, working together, and sharing responsibilities within a group. Didactic games emerged as one of the pedagogical tools that had the highest emotional impact during the study. Lessons organized on the basis of games aroused strong interest in students, associating the process of completing mathematical tasks with positive emotions.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study show that the process of forming interest in mathematics in primary school students has a complex psychological and pedagogical nature, which is closely related to several factors - motivation, cognitive development, emotional state and social environment. The results obtained confirm the importance of interactive methods and didactic approaches in increasing students' cognitive activity. It is emphasized in the pedagogical literature that the formation of students' internal motivation is one of the main factors of educational effectiveness. In particular, game and activity-based approaches significantly facilitate the process of knowledge acquisition in primary school students and form a positive emotional attitude in students [13]. This idea is consistent with the results of the study, since it was observed that when didactic games and interactive methods were used, students' activity and interest clearly increased.

It is also scientifically widely proven that the use of problem-based learning technologies is a very effective tool for developing independent thinking, critical thinking, and logical analysis skills in students. In modern pedagogical approaches, it is emphasized that problem-based learning forms the student not as a passive recipient of ready-made knowledge, but as an active participant in the search for knowledge, analysis, and drawing conclusions [14]. In the process of creating problem situations, students are given tasks of varying complexity, which encourages them to think about several solution options, compare alternative paths, and choose the most optimal solution. During the study, it can also be observed that students sought to solve the given problems not only using one method, but using different approaches, which indicated the development of

their creative and analytical thinking. The development of cognitive processes is also an important factor in forming interest in mathematics and increasing the effectiveness of educational activities. The harmonious and systematic development of mental processes such as attention, memory, perception, and thinking helps students to better understand the educational material and store it in long-term memory. Psychological studies have shown that the activation of these cognitive processes increases the ability to master mathematical concepts more quickly, analyze complex problems step by step, and effectively perform practical tasks [15]. The results of experimental studies also showed that students with an increased level of cognitive activity not only improved the quality of knowledge acquisition, but also significantly developed the skills of independent work and self-control.

In addition, the socio-psychological aspects of the educational environment are also one of the decisive factors in shaping students' attitudes and motivation towards their educational activities. A warm, trusting and supportive dialogue between the teacher and the student strengthens students' self-confidence and creates the basis for their active participation in the lesson process. Also, pedagogical methods such as encouragement, positive assessment and an individual approach form a positive attitude towards mathematical tasks in students and increase their interest in science. A favorable psychological environment is also indicated in the scientific literature as one of the most important factors that increase students' activity in educational activities [16]. The results of the study also confirm these ideas, showing that in classes with a positive environment, the level of participation, initiative and mastery of students is significantly higher.

In general, the results obtained and the analysis of available scientific sources show that the formation of interest in mathematics in primary school students requires an integrated approach. The combination of interactive methods, didactic games, problem-based learning and a favorable psychological environment significantly increases the cognitive activity of students and forms sustainable motivation.

CONCLUSION

1. Theoretical conclusion

The results of the study show that the formation of interest in mathematics in primary school students is a complex psychological and pedagogical process, which is closely related to motivation, cognitive development and social environment. In the development of mathematical thinking, age characteristics, cognitive needs and emotional state of students play an important role. Therefore, interactive and person-oriented approaches to organizing mathematics education are effective.

2. Practical conclusion

The results of the conducted pedagogical experiment confirmed that the use of interactive methods, didactic games and elements of problem-based learning significantly increases students' interest in the lesson. Students' desire for independent thinking, analysis and problem solving increased. Also, an increase in the level of active participation and mastery in the lesson process was observed.

3. General recommendation and final conclusion

In teaching mathematics in primary education, it is necessary to widely introduce modern pedagogical technologies, use playful and problem situations, and create a positive psychological environment. Cooperation between teachers, students, and parents is one of the main factors in increasing the effectiveness of education. In general, the formation of interest in mathematics

serves as an important basis for the intellectual development of students and future educational success.

REFERENCES

1. Vygotsky, L. S. (1982). *Thinking and speech*. Moscow: Pedagogy. 312 p.
2. Piaget, J. (2001). *The psychology of intelligence*. London: Routledge. 176 p.
3. Leontiev, A. N. (1977). *Activity, consciousness, and personality*. Moscow: Politizdat. 285 p.
4. Davletshin, M. G. (2002). *Age psychology*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi. 240 p.
5. Tolipov, O., & Usmonboeva, M. (2006). *Pedagogical technologies: Theory and practice*. Tashkent. 184 p.
6. Khodjayev, B. Kh. (2015). *Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical mastery*. Tashkent: Iqtisod-Moliya. 220 p.
7. Niyozov, A. N. (2018). *Methodology of teaching mathematics in primary grades*. Tashkent: Fan. 198 p.
8. Ganieva, M. (2019). *Innovative technologies in primary education*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi. 144 p.
9. Hasanboyeva, O. U. (2020). *Using interactive methods in the educational process*. Tashkent. 156 p.
10. Zunnunov, A. (2017). *Motivation and cognitive processes in education*. Tashkent. 172 p.
11. Shukurov, B. (2023). *Increasing the cognitive activity of primary school students*. Tashkent. 132 p.
12. Ergashev, S. (2016). *Methodology of pedagogical research*. Tashkent. 250 p.
13. Yusupov, Q. (2022). Using didactic games in mathematics lessons. *Journal of Pedagogy*, 3, 45–49.
14. Jabborova, D. (2021). Developing mathematical thinking in students. *Journal of Public Education*, 5, 33–37.
15. UNESCO. (2019). *Teaching and learning mathematics in primary education*. Paris. 210 p.
16. OECD. (2020). *Mathematics education in the 21st century*. Paris. 198 p.